

Title: Exploring the Potential of a Regional CoVE in Green Innovation: Insights from Skopje Region

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Abstract: This paper focuses on green transition and explores the potential of regional Centre of Vocational Excellence in Green Innovation in the Skopje Region, North Macedonia. The study involves engagement of key stakeholders through roundtable workshops and a quantitative survey, the analysis of which is a basis for the CoVE strategy. The findings present the opinions and perspectives of key actors from the quadruple helix, emphasising the importance of collaboration and partnership between different stakeholders and the need to continually assess and update educational programmes to prepare learners for the constantly evolving trends in the labour market. The CoVE in Green Innovation was established in December 2021 and in the moment its portfolio of services and capacities are being built.

Keywords: CoVE, green innovation, VET

1. Introduction

The world we are living in today is based on industrial development that prioritises sustainable practices and green initiatives. In this regard, the requirements of the industry, the labour market and the overall society, are constantly evolving. In order to remain competitive, current and future workers need to acquire new skills in an ongoing manner. This type of persistent and lifelong learning requires flexibility, curiosity, and a positive attitude towards gaining knowledge and developing or strengthening skills. Since 1948 and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, education became main pillar of equality and socio-economic development “Everyone has the right to education.” Furthermore, “it is the single best investment countries can make to build prosperous, healthy and equitable societies” (United Nations, n.d.). Considering the importance of the education, so-called Centres of Vocational Excellence (CoVEs) are receiving significant attention due to their ability to provide high quality skills to both young people and adults who will be able to respond to the emerging challenges and necessities (European Commission, n.d.). This paper presents a conducted analysis on what is needed for development of green innovation and what services of such CoVEs in Green Innovation can contribute to economic, environmental and social development in the Skopje Region, North Macedonia. Generally considered, vocational education and training (VET) are perceived as second-tier pathways to adulthood and the industry representatives are facing serious issues with lack of competent human resources (Velkovska, et al., 2022). To overcome this challenge, the Skopje Region has taken a proactive approach to advance vocational education and training in the field of Green Innovation. The findings presented in this paper are result of research that was conducted with engagement of key quadruple helix actors, who participated in roundtable workshops and quantitative survey. The study is part of a comprehensive research conducted within the project “European VET Excellence Platform for Green Innovation”, co-funded by the Erasmus+ programme of the European Union (www.greenovet.eu), which followed tailor-made methodological approach to establish regional Centres of Vocational Excellence in Green Innovation. The CoVE in Green Innovation was established in December 2021, as a body within the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University Ss. Cyril and Methodius in Skopje, with significant support and continuous engagement from the regional project consortium, National Centre for Development of Innovation and Entrepreneurial Learning, ASUC Boro Petrushevski, Rade Koncar TEP, Macedonian Chambers of Commerce.

2. Literature review

2.1. *VET and smart specialisation for green transition*

The emergency of the environmental crisis has raised awareness among the world’s population. “Green”, “eco”, “sustainable”, “renewables”, “zero-waste” are common buzzwords that are becoming integrated into many processes, initiatives, workflows. The necessity for environmental sustainability and responsible way of acting is not a questionable matter. Even

more, connecting green principles with technological development could lead to economic growth, as the implementation of green technologies reduces costs and waste, reduces utilisation of natural resources and increases competitive advantage (CEDEFOP; OECD, 2015) (Albort-Morant, Leal-Millán, & Cepeda-Carrión, 2016) (Weng, Chen, & Chen, 2015) (Wang, et al., 2021). In Europe, significant number of resources are dedicated to improving and promoting vocational education and training, which offers two key benefits: 1) economic benefits and 2) societal benefits (OECD, 2019). Education, formal or informal, is the foundation of growth, development, success and a better future for every individual. Each educational process should result with competent individuals who will contribute significantly to economic growth and a better society in the future. Well-developed vocational education and training systems can lead to high levels of employability and the capacity to respond quickly to changing trends in skills demand (OECD, 2019). One of the key initiatives in this regard are related to the establishment of Centres of Vocational Excellence, that are expected to stimulate local business communities and gaining knowledge. CoVEs bring together a wide range of local partners, such as providers of vocational education and training, employers, research centres, development agencies, and employment services (among others), to develop "skills ecosystems" that contribute to regional, economic and social development, innovation, and smart specialisation strategies (S3) (European Commission, n.d.). The smart specialisation approach is crucial since each region has its own problems, priority areas for intervention and opportunities for growth and development. The idea of the smart specialisation is to convert the needs, strengths and opportunities of a region into product and services placed on the market, through building a common vision for regional innovation (Foray, The Economic Fundamentals of Smart Specialization Strategies, 2017) (National Centre for Development of Innovation and Entrepreneurial Learning, 2019). One of the issues that our society is facing nowadays is that very often activities are undertaken to replicate strategies and good practices from the best regions, without taking into account the local challenges and opportunities. The constant strives to achieve the most and to be the best is an inevitable part of the society, but the wondering is what should be considered as the best? Valuable and innovative ideas in one region can be anchored in another region already, and vice versa. Smart specialisation emphasises the role of the entrepreneurial knowledge which involves scientific knowledge, technology and engineering, as well as understanding of the potential market growth, competitors and needed resources to undertake a particular initiative (Foray, From smart specialisation to smart specialisation policy, 2014).

The process of developing a smart specialisation strategy in North Macedonia is still ongoing. A mapping of the economic, scientific and innovation potential in the Republic of North Macedonia was carried out in 2019, in order to provide a good starting point for the identification of the main priorities in the preparation of the national strategy for smart specialisation (National Centre for Development of Innovation and Entrepreneurial Learning, 2019). The mapping resulted in identification of six promising areas for development and economic growth: 1) sustainable food and beverage production and value chains, 2) information and communication technologies, 3) smart/sustainable buildings and materials, 4) electrical equipment and machine parts, 5) sustainable tourism and hospitality, 6) energy for the future. Based on the mapped industrial priorities, in the period from August 2020 to February 2021, the national team for the development of smart specialisation has conducted a qualitative analysis of the promising priority areas, in order to provide essential information for the dialogue with stakeholders during the entrepreneurial discovery process (EDP) (Expert team of Economic Chamber of North Macedonia, 2021). The analysis resulted in four priority domains: 1) sustainable food and beverage production and value chains (smart agriculture, processing of food with high added value), 2) information and communication technologies (customised development of software solutions), 3) smart/sustainable buildings and materials, 4) electrical equipment and machine parts.

2.2. *Determining factors affecting development of green technologies and innovation*

The literature review covers overview of key factors that impact the green transition which are of various types, Table 1. Technological factors are related to the level of technological progress, research and development opportunities and available equipment. Then, the organisational factors are related to the organisational structure of the institution which undergoes transition, while the economic factors are closely related to those that are led by the environment and the market. It is worth pointing out that the listed factors are crucial for successful implementation of any kind of change. Given the factors that are presented, the development of green competences should begin with a review of what has already been developed and implemented, as well as an assessment of what is missing and needs to be introduced, or has potential for improvement. This research emphasises the importance of individual factors that include personal skills and competences to achieve a smooth green transition. Person's motivation, willingness and curiosity to acquire knowledge are of a high importance in any transition period.

Table 1. Determining factors affecting development of green technologies and innovation

Factor	Description	Source
Technological factors	Investments in research and development, materials, equipment, infrastructure, introduction and implementation of new technologies, university-industry cooperation, foreign investments	(Поленакoвiк, Марковска, Станковска, & Јовановски, 2019) (Stark, 2020) (Yin, Zhang, & Li, 2020) (Xia, Zhang, Yu, & Tu, 2019)
Environmental and market-dependent factors	Business models, focus on environment and environmental protection, capital investment, infrastructure, government policies, competitors, consumer demands	(Yin, Zhang, & Li, 2020) (Wang, et al., 2021) (Stark, 2020)
Regulatory incentives	Pollution prevention and control fees, green subsidies, low-interest loans, penalties for environmental irresponsibility	(Yin, Zhang, & Li, 2020) (Stark, 2020)
Organisational factors	Organisational leaders, organisational culture, organisational strategy, top management support	(Yin, Zhang, & Li, 2020) (Wang, et al., 2021) (Xia, Zhang, Yu, & Tu, 2019)
Normative and legal factors	Changes in laws and regulations, awareness and good knowledge of national and international laws, compliance with government plans, strategies and laws	(Wang, et al., 2021) (Поленакoвiк, Марковска, Станковска, & Јовановски, 2019)
Innovation orientation	Openness to new ideas, technologies, skills, resources and administrative systems, ability to effectively implement new services, systems and processes	(Wang, et al., 2021)
Individual (human) factors	Ability, talent, relevant knowledge, creativity, cognitive factors, upskilling (training to manage new machines and technologies), sustainability competences and after-sales services	(Поленакoвiк, Марковска, Станковска, & Јовановски, 2019) (Xia, Zhang, Yu, & Tu, 2019)
Environmental factors	Reducing the uncontrolled use of resources, directing them to their rational use	(Stark, 2020) (Гечевска, 2014)
Economic factors	Ensuring economic value, costs also play an important role	(Stark, 2020) (Гечевска, 2014)

3. Methodology

3.1. *Research model and methods*

The research model is developed within the GREENOVET project with the main aim to conduct strategic research, develop a strategy and establish a regional CoVE in Green

Innovation. The model for development of a viable CoVE in Green Innovation involves: 1) identification and engagement of key stakeholders, 2) conducting skills gap analysis for green innovation considering the regional (or national) smart specialisation, 3) conceptualisation and CoVE strategy development. The engagement of stakeholders and skills gap analysis are conducted as part of a comprehensive strategic research. The identification of representatives from educational, governmental, non-governmental and of course, the business community, who would be impacted by the CoVE or are able to provide some kind of support for its development, is necessary to recognise the needs and expectations of the regional ecosystem. The process of identification followed a predefined template with key information that should be provided, such as: brief description of the stakeholder, contact person details, stakeholder's influence on the project and foreseen impact on the stakeholder, importance of the identified stakeholders and an initial plan or actions to engage them.

Through regional roundtable workshop, those stakeholders were gathered together to discuss the existing knowledge and skills, as well as missing capacities and occupational profiles that could accelerate the green transition. In order to address wider audience, the research model involves quantitative survey with the main aim to measure the skills gap in green innovation, but also to perceive the sustainable awareness of the regional stakeholders and their readiness to develop VET excellence by using and offering services through the regional CoVE. The goal of the skills gap analysis is to assess the difference between the actual and future, desired state in regard to green innovation. The research phase and identification of such skills is highly important as it paves the way for introduction of the preferred changes towards a green transition (Polenakovikj, et al., 2022).

The insights from these activities are necessary for development of relevant strategy which is well-aligned with the priorities of the stakeholders and guides the CoVE staff to bridge the gap between the industry and the educational sector, with focus on vocational education. The strategy statement focuses on the strategic objectives, the scope of the CoVE, its key services, main partners and customers, as well as the competitive advantage. That strategy is a roadmap for achieving VET excellence providing clear overview of resource allocation and essential information for making timely and relevant decisions.

3.2. *Research instrument: Roundtable workshop*

In the beginning, January 2021, the key stakeholders were gathered together in a roundtable workshop, to discuss the status quo of the VET institutions and the overall educational system, with the aim to spot the biggest challenges and missing elements that are crucial for the labour market and for development of green innovation. 35 participants took part in the workshop and shared their valuable opinions on the following topics:

- 1) In general, which skills are provided by the VET institutions in the Skopje Region (or nationally)?
- 2) Which of the existing skills that a learner can acquire during the studies are relevant and needed for development of green innovation?
- 3) Apart from the skills that are already provided by (VET) educational institution, which skills are relevant for development of green mindset and finding green and sustainable solutions?
- 4) How can the missing elements be developed or strengthened in your environment? Is there a need for changes in the educational system, both formal and informal?

The results are highly important for development of regional CoVE in Green Innovation and presented in the findings section.

3.3. *Research instrument: Quantitative survey*

This study used a quantitative questionnaire since it is the most suitable instrument to attract a wider audience. The questionnaire was well-structured by using the online survey software QuestionPro. The target number for responses was set to be at least 90 totally completed and

relevant responses. The final analysis was conducted with gathered data from 92 responses. It is noteworthy to mention that some of the respondents belong to an organisation that fit into more than one sector. For instance, one company that operates in the field of sustainable tourism and hospitality, also produces its own food. The personal data of the respondents remains anonymous. However, they were carefully selected to possess the needed expertise and experience in their field in order to be able to detect the missing elements for development of green innovation and better collaboration between educational institutions and the business sector.

Table 2. Respondents' profile (N=92)

Variable	Sum of sample
Sector	
VET	30
Higher educational institution (HEI)	7
VET school	16
Public authority in charge of education/VET/green innovation	2
Other VET provider (NGO, CSO providing VET)	4
Enterprise	73
Company (Smart/sustainable buildings and materials)	4
Company (Sustainable food & beverage production & value chains)	14
Company (Sustainable tourism and hospitality)	4
Company (ICT)	9
Company (Energy for the future)	4
Company (Electrical equipment and machine parts)	7
Company (other industry)	19
Other	11
Size	92
Micro	18
Small	20
Medium	33
Large	21

4. Findings and discussion

4.1. Identifying existing and missing skills for development of Green Innovation

The initial findings are drawn from the roundtable workshop through a qualitative analysis, Table 3. Representatives from educational institutions (formal and informal), companies, civil associations and public institutions key to educational reforms and economic development, discussed about the needed skills and qualifications that could support and foster the green transition. Worthy of discussion is the fact that key stakeholders consider that critical and innovative thinking, focusing on challenges and the ability to develop new ideas, are the basic skills that every student needs, and acquires, during their educational process. It is a positive fact that both representatives from educational institutions and the business sector believe that the innovative way of thinking and addressing challenges to find solutions to overcome them are currently encouraged, which is especially important when talking about green concepts and technologies. In spite of that, there is a need for greater motivation, encouraging interest and creative thinking, and enabling flexibility in the educational process, in order to use those skills properly. Additionally, greening of personal, generic skills (soft skills) still seems to be missing. Curricula should include content that will bring green concepts closer to students, such as: description of the way green technologies work, overview of the latest green innovation, introducing and understanding the concept of circular economy, as well as developing awareness of extending products lifecycle, reusing and recycling.

Table 3. Workshop results: Identifying existing and missing skills for Green Innovation

Skills provided by VET institutions		Skills that need to be developed further
Basic skills	Skills for green innovation	Skills for green innovation
Critical thinking	Collaboration and communication with the business community	Awareness for green technologies and green innovation
Innovative thinking	Technical skills - energy efficiency	Practical implementation of the theoretical basis
Challenge-oriented thinking	Taking individual initiative	Understanding of the Circular Economy concept
Digital skills	Understanding of the environmental crisis and climate change	Motivation and perseverance
Literacy and language skills	Collaboration and communication with the non-governmental sector	Flexibility
Technical skills	Identifying solutions to protect the environment	Social entrepreneurship
Skills for work-based learning		Sustainable thinking
Skills for developing new ideas (creativity)		Skills for clean production
		Skills for recycling and reusing
		Water management
		Reversible logistics

The regional stakeholders who participated in the workshop agreed that for different areas there is a need for different actions. The missing skills cannot be developed properly without proper educational contents and study programmes, both formal and informal. Moreover, stakeholders firmly believe that the involvement of all relevant actors is crucial to develop and sustain the regional CoVE in Green Innovation. With the aim to implement a meaningful change, in this regard achieving VET excellence, fostering green and sustainable innovation, and supporting (self)employability of learners, it is essential to consider and take into account views, opinions and perspectives of all key actors in the region. In this way it can be ensured that the CoVE will be beneficial and sustainable and will have a positive impact on the community.

4.2. Benefit of potential services offered by the CoVE in Green Innovation

The research identified initial interest for CoVE’s services and benefits that it can offer to the key stakeholders in the region. The potential CoVE services and instruments are considered quite important and relevant for the stakeholders who took part in the survey, Table 4. Most of the respondents believe that it would be beneficial for them to establish or strengthen the contacts with the industry in order to collaborate on green and sustainable topics. Moreover, there is high interest for trainings, which in the moment of the research remain quite general and are being shaped with the development of CoVE’s portfolio of services. The findings reveal the interest in project endeavour and capacity building for developing project applications. On the other hand, the least attractive services are preselection of potential employees and announcements of job vacancies, indicating that respondents prefer services that facilitate skills development and training.

Table 4. Respondents' interest in CoVE services (N=92)

Variable	Frequency
Potential CoVE services	
Cooperation with industry	68
Trainings	64
Support for internship programs	57
Cooperation with VET providers	56
Support for project applications for international funding	52
Support for project applications for national funding	43
Preselection of potential employees (VET trainees)	24
Job vacancies announcement	16
Other	0

4.3. Supporting the regional CoVE in Green Innovation

The analysis shows that regional stakeholders identify their capacity, and the capacity of the organisation they are part of, to provide training in their area to expand the offerings of the CoVE and support its sustainability, Figure 1. Since approximately 70% of the respondents come from the industry, it is of great value to know that they are willing to share their knowledge and expertise in various kinds of trainings. Moreover, they are eager to collaborate further with the educational institutions and to provide case study examples and internships in order to ensure that the educational process is relevant and addressing current and future challenges.

Figure 1. Potential support for the CoVE by key stakeholders

5. Conclusions

The aim of this study was to assess the current state of VET in Skopje Region and identify the potential in terms of development of green skills, green technologies and green innovation, as well as the perspectives of key stakeholders. The stakeholders were encouraged to think in a sustainable way and imagine a greener future. It is evident that they recognise the importance of sustainability, circularity and the overall green transition, which is a good starting point for

the sustainability of the regional CoVE in Green Innovation. In addition to that, the importance of updating the existing curricula and providing more flexibility in the educational processes is emphasised. This is important for students to acquire the needed skills on the labour market. Overall, this study highlights the importance of collaboration and partnership between different stakeholders in developing sustainable solutions and the need to continually assess and update educational programmes to prepare learners for the constantly evolving trends in the labour market.

5.1. *Implications*

This study, accompanied by a skills gap analysis, served as a basis for development of a concept and strategy for the future functioning of the regional CoVE in Green Innovation. The CoVE was established in December 2021, and ever since its staff is collaborating to build its capacities, manage and sustain the CoVE and develop valuable portfolio of services. The analysis supports the CoVE by providing clearer insight on the direction in which it should be developed, based on the perspectives of quadruple helix actors in the region. Considering the importance of collaboration and providing links between different initiatives, the CoVE in Green Innovation is collaborating closely with the established FabLab (Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, 2022) and Learning Factory (Learn4SMEs: Learning Factory for Improving Digital Competitiveness and Industry 4.0 Readiness of SMEs in the Balkans, 2022) at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, in order to enable wider access to knowledge and connections with the industry that will contribute to smooth green transition, stronger research and innovation performance, but also higher competitiveness of our companies.

5.2. *Limitations and future research directions*

Significant measures were taken to ensure validity of the strategic research and collect statistical relevant data. However, this analysis served as a basis for establishing the CoVE, therefore the participants might not have been very well acquainted to the concept of the CoVE, and they may not have understood it as a network that will serve the regional ecosystem. For future research, it might be beneficial to conduct a more comprehensive survey with a wider range of respondents to enable more in-depth statistical analyses and to further support not only the CoVE development, but also its impact on the society. Considering the overall research, the Skopje Region is lagging behind because the smart specialisation strategy is not finalised yet. In the moment of the research, all available resources were used to align it with the recognised industry priorities in the region. However, future research should focus on integrating the final industry priorities and principles of smart specialisation into the core functioning of the CoVE in order to foster economic development and growth. By incorporating smart specialisation into the CoVE's operations, the Skopje Region can position itself more strategically within the European landscape. It is essential the region to invest in further research and innovation initiatives that will address the smart specialisation approach for development of responsible and sustainable solutions. In addition to this, taking into account the size of the country and the fact that the Skopje Region is the economic and educational centre of North Macedonia, the initiatives that are taken there have high potential to be replicated on a national level. The CoVE in Green Innovation established in the Skopje Region could be beneficial for all kinds of stakeholders around the country. Even more, as the first CoVE of its kind in the wider region, the Skopje CoVE in Green Innovation could provide valuable insights and lessons learned for other countries and regions looking to establish similar initiatives, and serve as a good model for strengthening the collaboration with the neighbouring countries and the region. Finally, it is vital to consider the principles of responsible research and innovation that facilitate the social-economic advancement in an open, transparent and inclusive manner. The CoVE development should ensure ethical principles, open access and inclusivity.

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